

Acta Medica Europa

Dental Aligners: A Paradigm Shift in Orthodontics?

Hassan Tariq¹

¹ Orthodontist, Alexandria, Virginia, USA

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10433043

Dear Editor,

The landscape of orthodontics is undergoing a significant transformation, with clear aligner therapy emerging as a popular alternative to traditional fixed braces. This letter aims to explore the potential and limitations of dental aligners, highlighting their clinical implications and addressing the need for evidence-based practice in this rapidly evolving field. Aligners offer a discreet and aesthetically pleasing option for teeth straightening, attracting both adults and teenagers seeking orthodontic treatment. Gradual tooth movement through a series of custom-made, removable trays distinguishes them from fixed braces, potentially enhancing comfort and oral hygiene (1-4).

Technological advancements such as 3D scanning and computer-aided design have refined treatment planning and aligner fabrication, contributing to their popularity. While effective for mild to moderate malocclusions, aligners may not be suitable for complex cases requiring significant tooth movement or skeletal adjustments. Patient compliance is crucial for successful treatment, as inconsistent aligner wear can compromise outcomes. Potential side effects like lispings, temporary tooth sensitivity, and gingival recession require informed discussion with patients before treatment initiation (5-7).

Despite the growing popularity of aligners, long-term data on their efficacy and safety compared to traditional braces are still limited. Rigorous clinical research is needed to establish robust evidence and optimize treatment protocols for various malocclusions. Standardized reporting guidelines and collaboration between manufacturers, clinicians, and researchers are essential in advancing the field of aligner therapy. Dental aligners offer a valuable addition to the orthodontist's armamentarium, but should not be considered a universal replacement for traditional braces. Careful patient selection, comprehensive treatment planning, and continuous monitoring throughout the course of therapy are crucial for successful outcomes. The future of orthodontics likely lies in a hybrid approach, utilizing both aligner and fixed brace

technology based on individual patient needs and the complexity of the malocclusion (3-6).

The emergence of dental aligners has undoubtedly broadened the scope of orthodontic treatment, offering patients a more discreet and potentially comfortable option. However, robust evidence and a patient-centered approach remain paramount for ensuring safe and effective outcomes. Continued research and collaboration are essential in shaping the future of this rapidly evolving field and ensuring optimal oral health for patients seeking orthodontic treatment.

REFERENCES

1. Tartaglia GM, Mapelli A, Maspero C, et al. Direct 3D Printing of Clear Orthodontic Aligners: Current State and Future Possibilities. *Materials* (Basel). 2021;14(7):1799. Published 2021 Apr 5. doi:10.3390/ma14071799
2. Rossini G, Parrini S, Castroflorio T, Deregibus A, Debernardi CL. Efficacy of clear aligners in controlling orthodontic tooth movement: a systematic review. *Angle Orthod*. 2015;85(5):881-889. doi:10.2319/061614-436.1
3. Nucera R, Dolci C, Bellocchio AM, et al. Effects of Composite Attachments on Orthodontic Clear Aligners Therapy: A Systematic Review. *Materials* (Basel). 2022;15(2):533. Published 2022 Jan 11. doi:10.3390/ma15020533
4. Zinelis S, Panayi N, Polychronis G, Papageorgiou SN, Eliades T. Comparative analysis of mechanical properties of orthodontic aligners produced by different contemporary 3D printers. *Orthod Craniofac Res*. 2022;25(3):336-341. doi:10.1111/ocr.12537
5. Papageorgiou SN, Koletsi D, Iliadi A, Peltomaki T, Eliades T. Treatment outcome with orthodontic aligners and fixed appliances: a systematic review with meta-analyses. *Eur J Orthod*. 2020;42(3):331-343. doi:10.1093/ejo/cjz094
6. Al-Nasser L, Lamster IB. Prevention and management of periodontal diseases and dental caries in the older adults. *Periodontol* 2000. 2020;84(1):69-83. doi:10.1111/prd.12338
7. Rossini G, Parrini S, Castroflorio T, Deregibus A, Debernardi CL. Periodontal health during clear aligners treatment: a systematic review. *Eur J Orthod*. 2015;37(5):539-543. doi:10.1093/ejo/cju083